

Question	Codes	Respondents	Percentage	Question	Codes	Respondents	Percentage	
Background	Legal sciences	7	19,44%	Which knowledge? (Could be more than one)	Python	22	44,00%	
	Communication	3	8,33%		Shell	1	2,00%	
	Education and humanities	3	8,33%		Javascript	9	18,00%	
	Management, economics, and politics	6	16,67%		React	1	2,00%	
	Health and life sciences	5	13,89%		HTML + CSS	4	8,00%	
	Technology (architecture, engineering, etc.)	9	25,00%		Java	3	6,00%	
	Elementary education	2	5,56%		Swift	3	6,00%	
	Education in physics	1	2,78%		VBA	1	2,00%	
Prior knowledge	No prior knowledge	18	50,00%		Ruby / Rails	1	2,00%	
	Yes	18	50,00%		SQL	2	4,00%	
Knowledge application	Career change	22	61,11%		Django	1	2,00%	
	Skills for current career	12	33,33%		R	2	4,00%	
	Graduation requirement	1	2,78%		Total	50	100,00%	
	Hobby / Curiosity	1	2,78%		Youtube videos	18	32,73%	
When start learning	Less than 2 weeks	1	2,78%		Taking online courses	15	27,27%	
	Up to a month	3	8,33%		Taking face-to-face courses	9	16,36%	
	Six months	2	5,56%		Reading documentation	2	3,64%	
	A year	13	36,11%		Mentorship	1	1,82%	
	Two years	3	8,33%		Books / Magazines / Manuscripts	5	9,09%	
	More than two years.	14	38,89%	Through work experience	2	3,64%		
Challenges (Could be more than one)	Challenges regarding career transition	3	7,89%	Bootcamp	1	1,82%		
	Correct order of content	5	13,16%	In practical projects	2	3,64%		
	English	2	5,26%	Total	55	100,00%		
	Equipment limitations	1	2,63%	Relationship with previous education	No relationship	13	36,11%	
	Frustration and loss of motivation	6	15,79%		Partially related	19	52,78%	
	Logical mindset	11	28,95%		Strongly related	4	11,11%	
	Methodology	6	15,79%		Initiatives/projects resulting from learning	No Initiatives/projects	17	47,22%
	Technology itself	4	10,53%			Yes, but for work / clients / research	11	30,56%
	Total	38	1	Yes, focused on learning		4	11,11%	
Age	18 - 25	8	22,22%	Yes, for personal projects		4	11,11%	
	25 - 35	17	47,22%	Relationship with previous education		No relationship	13	36,11%
	35+	11	30,56%		Partially related	19	52,78%	
Recommends to others in their field	yes, As a new knowledge	18	50,00%		Strongly related	4	11,11%	
	yes, for changing careers	8	22,22%		Initiatives/projects resulting from learning	No Initiatives/projects	17	47,22%
	yes but not detailed why	5	13,89%	Yes, but for work / clients / research		11	30,56%	
	not recommend	5	13,89%	Yes, focused on learning		4	11,11%	
			Yes, for personal projects	4		11,11%		
			Yes, for personal projects	4		11,11%		